

MEDIA DEVELOPMENT TRENDS IN KASHKADARYA**Norturayev Sukhrob Erkin ugli****Karshi State University PhD student****<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3621-2944>****UDK: 117:004-2:102.4(111:07)****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19543779>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 07th April 2026Accepted: 09th April 2026Online: 11th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

Kashkadarya television, territorial television, media development, tarihi television, Aether dastructor, development technician, development organization, local neighborhood news, journalism, cultural signaling

ABSTRACT

This article presents a comprehensive analysis of the history and development of the television system in the Kashkadarya region. Particular attention is given to the establishment and early activities of regional television, and a structural examination is given of the stages of its acquisition of modern technical equipment, broadcasting mechanisms, initial broadcasting projects, and television program development. The study provides a historical perspective on the reforms implemented during the years of independence, the liberalization of the television system, and its integration with modern technical standards. It also analyzes the socio-cultural significance of local television in shaping the regional information space, its role in satisfying the information needs of the population, and its influence on the development of the regional cultural environment and public life through local creative and journalistic activities.

Introduction. Television is one of the mass media that plays an important role in disseminating information in society, covering social processes, and promoting cultural and educational ideas. Since the second half of the 20th century, television has become widespread in countries around the world and has become an important part of public life. The television system in Uzbekistan began to take shape in the 1950s and 1960s. In the republic, along with central television, great attention was paid to providing the population with local information by organizing regional television studios. In this process, the television system was gradually formed in the Kashkadarya region. Kashkadarya regional television served as an important source of information in covering the social, economic, and cultural life of the local population. Its history is inextricably linked not only with the development of mass media, but also with the socio-political and cultural development of the region.

Literature review. Although general information on the history of the establishment and development of regional TV channels in Uzbekistan is reflected in the treatises and books of A. Karimov, M. Masharipov, E.B. Mahmudov, V.Z. Zuparov, O.A. Kholmatov, M. Ro'ziev, Kh. Ju'raev, T.A. Akhmedov, I.S. Yusupov, the activities of the Kashkadarya regional TV channel are not given sufficient space. At the same time, it indicates the need to introduce into scientific

circulation and draw scientific conclusions articles on the topic that provide information about the development directions of regional TV channels.

Research methodology. Historical analysis, chronological, sequential, comparative analysis and content analysis methods were used to cover the topic. Also, archival documents, scientific literature and materials related to the media served as the main sources. The study analyzed the stages of development of the television system from a historical perspective.

Results and discussion. The history of the emergence of television has been studied by researchers in several stages. The ideas for creating television began to take shape at the beginning of the 20th century, and its development process is conditionally divided into several periods. In particular, in 1920–1935, mechanical television was launched, while in 1936–1966, electronic black-and-white television became widespread [1:11]. Since 1967, electronic color television has been developed, and since the 2000s, digital television technologies have been introduced. In recent years, high-quality television images have been achieved as a result of the use of vacuum-free transmitters and modern imaging devices, as well as technologies for converting image and sound signals into digital form. On this basis, digital TV, hard disk TV, and stereo color TV have appeared. Television broadcasting in Uzbekistan was officially launched on November 5, 1956 in Tashkent. In the same year, the Tashkent Television Studio was established. The programs prepared from this studio were broadcast via the Tashkent Television Tower, which is 180 meters high. From January 1, 1973, Uzbek television programs also began to be broadcast in color.

On January 7, 1992, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the transformation of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Television and Radio Broadcasting into the State Television and Radio Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan” was issued[2:18]. Based on this Decree, broad opportunities were created for the development of the television and radio broadcasting organization in the country, coordination of its work with television and radio organizations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regions, and, in turn, foreign countries, and improvement of the legal framework of the sector’s activities.

On March 28, 1994, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to increase the volume of programs and broadcasts of the State Television and Radio Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan, strengthen its material and technical base” was adopted[3:2]. Based on it, the uninterrupted operation of 3 state television channels was ensured. The volume of broadcasts was increased to 16.5 hours, and the volume of television's own creative products was increased to 10 hours [4:72].

As a result of the special attention paid to the development of the mass media system in the country during the years of independence, regional television networks also began to form.

The history of the formation and development of the television system in the Kashkadarya region can also be scientifically analyzed by dividing it into three stages. This classification allows us to consistently cover the establishment, institutional development and modern stage of regional television. Its first stage covers the years 1970–1995. This period is considered the period of formation of the Kashkadarya television infrastructure. Although independent television was not established in the Kashkadarya region during this period, the formation of the infrastructure is observed. In particular, during this period, retransmission

stations were built to receive and distribute republican television programs in the regions. As a result, the population of the region had the opportunity to watch Tashkent television broadcast programs. Also, the technical base in the field of radio communications and telecommunications in the territory of the Kashkadarya region was gradually improved. During this period, work was carried out to train local personnel and cooperate with the republican media outlets. These events served as an important preparatory stage for the subsequent establishment of an independent television station in the region.

The next stage covers the years 1995–2005. During this period, the Kashkadarya Regional Television was established and became a period of institutional development. On January 23, 1995, a decision was made to establish the Kashkadarya Regional Television. Based on this decision, 200 thousand US dollars were allocated to purchase modern equipment for the regional television. Modern equipment was imported from abroad in exchange for this money. On August 24 of the same year, at 5:00 p.m., the first broadcast of the Kashkadarya Television was broadcast. Although the first broadcasts were broadcast for a limited time, the volume of the broadcast later expanded. During this period, a creative team of local journalists, cameramen and directors was formed, and information and cultural and educational programs dedicated to the life of the region began to be prepared. Thus, the Kashkadarya Television became an important factor in the formation of the regional information space.

On August 25, 1997, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the comprehensive re-equipment of the system of the TV and Radio Company of Uzbekistan with equipment” was published [5:64]. In accordance with the Resolution, during 1998-2006, the State Unitary Enterprise “Republican TV and Radio Center”, the State Unitary Enterprise “Uzbekistan Telefilm” and the TV and radio companies of Namangan, Kashkadarya, and Samarkand regions were equipped with the most modern equipment manufactured by the Austrian companies “Siemens AG” and “BFE AG” from Germany.

Since the 2000s, a new stage has begun in the activities of the Kashkadarya regional television. During this period, the development of information and communication technologies has also affected the television industry. Modern technical equipment has been introduced in the TV studio, and work has been carried out to switch to a digital broadcasting system. This has served to improve the quality of TV programs and expand broadcasting opportunities. At the same time, television has expanded the ability to quickly cover social, economic, and cultural processes in the region. Television has become an important tool in meeting the information needs of the local population.

On December 27, 2001, a new building was built and put into operation for the Kashkadarya TV and Radio Company [6:1]. At that time, the TV center, equipped in accordance with the requirements of the time, began broadcasting informational and partly socio-economic, cultural and educational programs 3 days a week, namely on Wednesdays, Fridays, and Sundays, for 30 minutes each [7:1]. By 2002, two “SONY BETAKAM SP” television cameras and two sets of “SONY BETAKAM SP” simple linear editing tables were delivered and installed for the regional TV and Radio Company. By 2003, three-camera studio equipment from the “BFE SIEMENS” company (Germany) was installed in the regional TV and Radio

Company [8:64]. As a result, the regional television's broadcasting hours were extended to 6 hours, allowing it to go on the air every day except Monday.

The third stage began in 2005, and this period is characterized by increased modernization work in the television sector and the development of digital technologies. Starting in 2007, the regional television's broadcasting hours were extended to 8 hours. Starting in April 2008, the regional television's broadcasting hours were further expanded as a result of the regional television's programs being broadcast on a separate channel.

In short, the history of Kashkadarya regional television was formed in several stages. The creation of television infrastructure and the beginning of the activity of the television studio in the Soviet era formed the basis of this industry. In the 1970s and 1980s, television programs were enriched in content and local journalistic personnel began to form. In the years of independence, the promotion of national ideas, historical heritage and spiritual values became one of the main directions of television activity. Today, Kashkadarya regional television plays an important role in shaping the regional information space and fulfills the task of providing the population with fast and reliable information.

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